

Supplementary Information

Gold/Gold Oxide as a Solid State On-Chip pH Sensing Probe
for Food Applications

Supplementary information Figure 1 (A to K) show average cyclic voltammograms for the real-world samples cycled between 0.2 V to 1.4 V or 0.3 V to 1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl at 50 mV s⁻¹ at room temperature.

Supplementary Figure 1: (A) cyclic voltammogram of Caramel flavoured coffee cycled between 0.3 V and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. (B) CV of low-fat milk cycled between 0.3 V and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. (C) CV of Green Tea cycled between 0.2 V and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. (D) CV of protein enriched yogurt cycled between 0.3 V and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl. (E) CV of Mango and orange juice between 0.2 V and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl (F) CV of orange Juice cycled between 0.4 and 1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (G) CV of Apple Juice cycled between 0.3 and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl (H) CV of Lemon flavoured tea cycled between 0.4 and 1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (I) CV of Vitamin enriched juice cycled between 0.4 and 1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (J) CV of Lemon and lime flavoured soda cycled between 0.3 and 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl (K) CV of Orange soda cycled between 0.4 and 1.5 V vs Ag/AgCl

Supplementary Table S1 shows a comparison of commercial glass pH probe and gold/gold oxide pH sensor for the relevant samples with the mean difference between the gold/gold oxide pH sensor and the commercial glass pH probe and the percentage error.

The percentage error between glass electrode pH and gold oxide pH was calculated using the given equation;

$$\text{Error (\%)} = \frac{pH_{pH_glass\ pH\ meter} - pH_{Gold\ Oxide\ Sensor}}{pH_{pH_glass\ pH\ meter}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Table S1: pH values of real-world samples with comparison of commercial glass electrode compared to gold oxide electrochemical sensor. The pH difference and percentage difference

Sample	Glass pH probe	Gold Sensor pH	Delta pH	% Difference
Caramel Flavoured Coffee	6.71	7.00	-0.29	4.32 %
Low Fat Milk	6.57	6.70	0.13	1.97 %
Green Tea	6.13	6.10	0.03	0.49 %
Protein Enriched Yogurt	4.39	4.20	0.19	4.32 %
Mango/Orange Juice	3.67	3.65	-0.02	0.45 %
Orange Juice	3.96	3.92	0.04	1.01 %
Apple Juice	3.4	3.50	0.1	2.90 %
Lemon Flavored Tea Drink	3.29	3.39	0.1	3.04 %
Vitamin enriched soda	3.14	3.20	-0.06	1.91 %
Lemon and lime soda	3.24	3.25	-0.01	0.31 %
Orange soda	2.95	3.00	-0.05	1.69 %